

Monte Carlo Sampling Strategy for a Non-Perturbative Approach to the Neutron Noise Equation: a New Eigenvalue Formulation and Application to the Analysis of Fuel Assembly Vibrations

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, several Monte Carlo solvers have been developed to solve the Fourier-transformed Boltzmann equation, motivated by the need of performing high-fidelity simulations of the neutron noise field in the frequency domain. These numerical tools usually rely on the 'orthodox' linearization, a first-order approach that consists in neglecting the product of perturbed quantities. The accuracy of this approximation is known to be rather limited in the case of noise induced by mechanical vibrations. In view of this consideration, in a recent work we have proposed a proof of concept for a non-perturbative approach to the noise equation based on an eigenvalue formulation suitable for Monte Carlo simulation. In this work, we present further advances on this computational strategy, and we rephrase the underlying eigenvalue formulation in order to broaden its range of validity. An application to a one-dimensional vibration model is illustrated. Overall, the proposed strategy shows great potential for the simulation of the noise resulting from mechanical vibrations, significantly improving the performance of the non-perturbative noise computation with respect to previous attempts.

Keywords: Neutron noise, Monte Carlo, Non-perturbative approach, Vibrations

1. INTRODUCTION

Power reactor noise describes the fluctuations of the neutron flux around its average value arising from various perturbations of the core, typically due to temperature and density variations, or to vibrations of reactor components induced by fluid-structure interactions [1]. The analysis of the neutron noise is used to detect, characterize and localize the sources of core anomalies, and thus represents a valuable asset for reactor safety [1]. Pioneering attempts at determining the noise field stemming from a given perturbation relied on analytical treatments using single-speed diffusion theory, along with several approximations; for a review, see e.g. Ref. 2. Significant progress towards high-fidelity numerical simulation of neutron noise has been achieved in the last fifteen years, encompassing the development of multi-group deterministic solvers (using transport or diffusion theory, either in the time or frequency domain), or Monte Carlo solvers in the frequency domain [3, 4, 5, 6]. Monte Carlo solvers for the noise equation require the estimation of complex-valued quantities, which is achieved through special games using complex-valued particle weights, in lieu of the usual (real and positive) statistical weights [7]. These algorithms were later improved in terms of accuracy and efficiency; in particular, weight cancellation techniques proved critical for noise problems induced by mechanical vibrations [4, 8].

Usually, the derivation of the noise equation (i.e. the Boltzmann equation with time-dependent cross sections representing the effects of the perturbations) involves an approximation dubbed 'orthodox'

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linearization [9]: the perturbation and the noise field resulting from the perturbation are assumed to be ‘small’, and their product is neglected. In the frequency (Fourier-transformed) domain, this allows for a decoupled treatment, since a noise source at a given frequency only produces noise at that frequency. Linear theory has proven accurate and efficient in many circumstances, but is known to fail in specific applications, encompassing mechanical vibrations [9, 10, 2]. A non-perturbative noise (NPN) approach, i.e. tackling the full noise equation without linearization, may be considered for such cases [11, 2]. In the case of mechanical vibrations, it has been shown in particular that the NPN has great potential for improved fidelity, and correctly predicts the behavior of higher noise harmonics [2]. The numerical approach for NPN chosen in Ref. 2 relied on a deterministic solver, where inner iterations took care of a frequency-coupled variant of the linear noise equation, and outer iterations carried out corrections to the transport operator to account for reactivity effects. Motivated by the interest of the NPN for applications, in Ref. 12 we have proposed a novel computational strategy for the non-linearized noise equation based on an eigenvalue formulation that is suitable for Monte Carlo methods, contrary to the earlier implementations. Such an algorithm was implemented in the Monte Carlo mini-app MGMC [13] and successfully tested for a simple point-reactor model [12].

By building on our previous findings, in this work we present the latest advances of the NPN algorithm, and discuss a more challenging application to a one-dimensional fuel assembly vibration model. In Section 2, we will recall the main features of the NPN algorithm and we describe its recent evolutions. We will focus in particular on a reformulation of the eigenvalue problem that enables significant computational advantages. We will then illustrate our numerical results for the vibration model in Section 3. Conclusions will be finally drawn in Section 4.

2. MONTE CARLO NON-PERTURBATIVE ALGORITHM FOR NEUTRON NOISE

The derivation of the NPN algorithm and the analysis of the key differences with respect to the linear noise theory were provided in Ref. 12, to which we refer the readers for further details. The non-linearized neutron noise equation in the frequency domain can be rewritten as

$$\left(\frac{i\omega}{v} + \vec{\Omega} \cdot \nabla + \hat{\Sigma}_{t,0} - \hat{S}_0 \right) \hat{\phi} + \frac{1}{2\pi} (\delta\hat{\Sigma}_t - \delta\hat{S}) * \hat{\phi} = \frac{1}{k} \left(\hat{\mathcal{F}}_0 \hat{\phi} + \frac{1}{2\pi} \delta\hat{\mathcal{F}} * \hat{\phi} \right), \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\phi}$ is the Fourier-transformed neutron flux, ω the angular frequency, $\vec{\Omega}$ the direction, v the speed, Σ_t the total cross section, \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{F} the scattering operator and fission operator, respectively, and i the imaginary unit; the ‘hat’ and the asterisk denote Fourier-transformed quantities and convolution product, respectively. The Fourier-transformed terms carrying an index ‘0’ stem from the average components of the operators, whereas the Fourier-transformed terms with a ‘ δ ’ stem from the time-dependent (perturbed) components. Variables are implicit.

Equation (1) takes the form of an eigenvalue problem, in that it involves a transport operator on the left-hand side and a production operator on the right-hand side, both acting on the unknown $\hat{\phi}$, with eigenvalue k . The eigenvalue k that divides the fission source in Equation (1) ensures the existence of periodic solutions and prevents any power drift. Note that k generally differs from the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} . Equation (1) can be solved by power iteration by suitably modifying existing Monte Carlo codes, provided that a few unusual features are taken into account: complex quantities, angular frequency ω as an additional phase-space variable, and operators involving convolution products.

Complex quantities are dealt with by allowing for complex-valued particle weights, in lieu of the usual (real and positive) statistical weights [7, 4]. Either of two available methods to interpret the Fourier-transformed time-derivative term $i\omega/v$ can be used: in the flight-based method, this term induces a shift of the weight phase during flights, whereas in the collision-based method this term is interpreted as a new collision event, leading to a copy of the incident particle with a weight multiplier. Population control can be enforced on the complex-valued particle weights using e.g. a norm-based Russian roulette, which has shown satisfactory convergence properties [14].

The noise field is estimated simultaneously at all frequencies by using ω as an additional phase-space variable. Since we are only concerned with periodic solutions resulting from perturbations at a given angular frequency ω_0 , each particle stores its frequency as an integer $h = \omega/\omega_0$, the discrete index of the noise *harmonic*. Simulations are truncated at harmonic h_{\max} , ignoring any transfer from and to higher harmonics. Particles having index h only contribute to tallies of $\hat{\phi}_h = \hat{\phi}(h\omega_0)$. The symmetry of the Fourier coefficients of real-valued functions is leveraged to restrict the noise computation to $h \geq 0$, by adding a *frequency mirror* at the null harmonic.

The convolution products are handled as new collision types, for each harmonic of the perturbation. The definition of convolution products implies that the outgoing particles are sampled similarly as for the corresponding usual reaction, except that the particle harmonic is additionally shifted: an incident particle at harmonic h that undergoes such a reaction for a perturbation at angular frequency $p\omega_0$ will produce particles at harmonic $h' = h + p$.

Moreover, Monte Carlo games involving power iteration combined with non-positive weights mandatorily require weight cancellation techniques to ensure proper convergence towards a *physical* solution [15]. The simplest weight cancellation method, called the binning procedure, sums up particle weights on a mesh at the end of each power iteration generation, and takes the average on each cell to cancel out contributions with opposite signs [7]. Finally, normalization is applied after weight cancellation, using the total statistical weight of the population, i.e. the sum of the absolute values of the weights of all the particles.

2.1. Rephrasing the Eigenvalue Problem

The eigenvalue formulation of Equation (1) implies that the particles produced by $\delta\hat{\mathcal{F}}$ should be sent to the next generation, and those produced by $\delta\hat{\Sigma}_t$ and $\delta\hat{\mathcal{S}}$ should be recycled inside the current generation. Since $\hat{\Sigma}_{t,0}$ (the time-average of Σ_t) remains unchanged, these productions are not compensated by absorption. For large enough perturbations, the noise computation becomes *super-critical inside a generation* and cannot be carried out. Numerical investigations have shown that this limitation was severe, preventing the application of the original form of NPN to most of the usual neutron noise benchmark problems. Thus, we chose a different strategy: all $\delta\hat{\mathcal{F}}$, $\delta\hat{\mathcal{S}}$ and $\delta\hat{\Sigma}_t$ productions are sent to the next generation. This ensures sub-criticality inside each generation and corresponds to a new eigenvalue formulation:

$$\left(\frac{i\omega}{v} + \vec{\Omega} \cdot \nabla + \hat{\Sigma}_{t,0} - \hat{\mathcal{S}}_0 \right) \hat{\phi} = \frac{1}{k'} \left(\hat{\mathcal{F}}_0 \hat{\phi} + \frac{1}{2\pi} (\delta\hat{\mathcal{F}} + \delta\hat{\mathcal{S}} - \delta\hat{\Sigma}_t) * \hat{\phi} \right). \quad (2)$$

The eigenvalue k' in Equation (2) is generally different from k in Equation (1), and cannot be assigned a simple meaning. Similarly to regular criticality calculations, noise calculations are only physically relevant when k' is close to unity.

The formulation in Equation (1) has only fission as a generation source. Fission is generally assumed to be isotropic, with emission spectra independent of the incoming particle energy: for weight cancellation at the end of each generation, having only fission source terms means that we can disregard particle direction and energy. The formulation in Equation (2) forgoes this perk. To overcome this complication, we decided to use *partial* cancellation, only applied on fission particles; all other productions are sent directly to the next generation. This method reduces the efficiency of weight cancellation, and might thus incur problems when the perturbation amplitude is too strong. However, the severe limitations of the previous implementation are successfully removed, as illustrated in the numerical applications.

3. APPLICATION: THE ROD MODEL

The NPN Monte Carlo algorithm was applied to the *rod model* benchmark from Ref. 2. Neutrons are bound to move either left or right at a constant speed $v = 2.2 \times 10^5$ cm/s on a rod of total length $L =$

10 cm, made of a centered fuel pin of length $d = 6$ cm surrounded by a moderator. The two interfaces between fuel and moderator are vibrating at frequency $\omega_0/2\pi = 0.1$ Hz and amplitude $\varepsilon = 0.5$ cm. Scattering is isotropic. In the moderator, the scattering and capture cross sections are $\Sigma_s = 3.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\Sigma_c = 0.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; in the fuel, the scattering, capture and fission cross sections are $\Sigma_s = 1.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\Sigma_c = 1.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\Sigma_f = 0.98 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; the fission multiplicity is $\nu = 2.2711$, the delayed neutron fraction is $\beta = 7 \times 10^{-3}$, and the precursor decay constant is $\lambda = 8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Figure 1 compares the simulation results of the NPN Monte Carlo algorithm for the first few noise harmonics to those of the default linear noise algorithm of MGMC. Exact noise source sampling is used to model vibrations [8]. In linear theory, the critical flux is the flux-time average, i.e. the 0th harmonic. To validate our results, an *ad hoc* deterministic solver was further implemented, using the finite-difference method. The generalized eigenvalue problem in Equation (2) is implicitly cast into an ordinary one by solving the corresponding linear system when required, using the GMRES method

Figure 1. Noise of the rod model. Coordinates $x = 2$ and $x = 8$ denote the boundaries of the vibrating fuel pin. Left to right: Real and imaginary part. Top to bottom: 0th, 1st, 2nd harmonics. The top plots show values, the bottom plots show difference between Monte Carlo and deterministic computations.

Figure 2. Convergence of the eigenvalue k' (left) and entropy H (right) with respect to generations. Colored lines represent independent replicas. The black line is the average of the replicas.

[16]. The ordinary eigenvalue problem is itself solved by the ARPACK implementation of the Implicitly Restarted Arnoldi Method [17]. Monte Carlo and deterministic methods are coherent up to the 2nd harmonic, as shown in Figure 1. Discrepancies are however observed at the 3rd harmonic, not displayed here: investigations are ongoing in order to elucidate their origin.

The difference between linear noise and non-perturbative noise observed at the 1st and 2nd harmonic are coherent with results from Ref. 2, the 2nd harmonic being in particular poorly approximated by linear theory. On the contrary, there is almost no difference in the 0th harmonic (i.e. the time-average); the larger discrepancy found in Ref. 2 is deemed to be spurious.

Besides, simulations were also successfully performed with the Monte Carlo NPN algorithm at frequencies 10 Hz and 100 Hz, both lying in the plateau region. A tentative variance-reduction technique was also tested, in the form a basic weight window between harmonics, but yielded poor performances. Due to limited space, these investigations will be reported in a forthcoming work.

3.1. Inactive Generations

The NPN Monte Carlo algorithm relies on power iteration, and thus requires a user-defined number of inactive generations for the particle source to converge. Figure 2 illustrates the behavior of two usual indicators to monitor convergence: the value of k' and the entropy at each generation. For this purpose, we use the Shannon entropy on the harmonic dimension only, i.e. $H = -\sum \frac{W_h}{W} \log_2 \frac{W_h}{W}$, where W is the total statistical weight of the population and W_h the total statistical weight in harmonic h . Estimates are obtained from 20 independent simulations. The entropy seems to reach equilibrium in about 800 to 1000 generations, while the k' values converge faster, as expected. Although slower than usual critical computations, the convergence is faster than in our preliminary implementation of the NPN [12]. The convergence speed depends on the dominance ratio, which is related to the coupling of the system induced by the perturbation. Therefore, the smaller the perturbation, the higher the number of required inactive cycles will be, and conversely.

3.2. Harmonic truncation

In Monte Carlo, Equation (2) is likely to be truncated at a given harmonic h_{\max} . Taking a large h_{\max} will reduce the truncation bias, but will also reduce the number of particles in the harmonics of interest, which induces higher variance. Therefore, simulations with large h_{\max} may not be affordable.

Computations were performed with the NPN Monte Carlo algorithm for h_{\max} ranging from 1 to 7. Figure 3 presents the relative difference between a representative set of results and the one at $h_{\max} = 7$,

Figure 3. Relative difference of the noise field for linear theory and NPN algorithm with different values of h_{\max} , compared to a chosen reference at $h_{\max} = 7$. Coordinates $x = 2$ and $x = 8$ denote the boundaries of the vibrating fuel pin. Left is 1st harmonic, right is 2nd harmonic.

used as a reference. The 0th harmonic, not presented here, shows little difference between different values of h_{\max} . For the first harmonic, linear theory already provides a good estimate; raising h_{\max} progressively reduces the bias. For the second harmonic, $h_{\max} = 2$ retrieves most of the NPN correction, yet with a statistically significant difference, while $h_{\max} = 3$ provides a result statistically indistinguishable from the reference. Higher harmonics $h \geq 3$, not represented here, lie within the error bars of the reference, even for $h_{\max} = h$. Altogether, considering that one is reasonably interested in the first two harmonics at most, $h_{\max} = 3$ is deemed sufficient in this case. This finding should be confirmed once discrepancies on the 3rd harmonic are resolved.

3.3. Performance

Performance of computations has been quantified using the Figure of Merit (FoM) $1/(\sigma^2 T)$, with σ the standard deviation and T the computation time, averaged on all detector positions. Estimates of σ used 20 independent replicas for NPN, and 10^4 pseudo-independent replicas for linear noise, with source re-sampling separated by 20 power iteration generations. Reducing the skipped generations to 3 in linear noise simulations would slightly increase the actual variance of the results and reduce time by about 30%. Estimated FoMs corresponding to this simplified linear calculations are given in parentheses.

Using NPN rather than linear theory improved the FoM by a factor 2.9 (resp. 2.0) on the 1st harmonic and 1.2 (resp. 0.8) on the 2nd harmonic. Since NPN computes both harmonics simultaneously, obtaining the same precision on both harmonics with linear computations would therefore require 4.0 (resp. 2.8) times longer (furthermore, linear theory is known to be inaccurate for the 2nd harmonic). This acceleration is likely due to linear theory using a fixed-source computation in a nearly-critical system, whereas NPN relies on the power iteration. In addition, NPN ensures a higher number of particles sent to weight cancellation, which improves its efficiency.

3.4. A hierarchy of approximations

We discuss now the different available approximations of the neutron noise equation. Figure 4 presents results obtained by our *ad hoc* deterministic solver on the rod model benchmark, for supposedly decreasing levels of approximation, using the NPN k' formulation as a reference. The default linear theory has already been discussed. All other simulations account for the *new-steady-state* (NS), i.e. taking into account the average of the perturbation (into the '0' subscript operators), both during critical flux

Figure 4. Absolute difference of the noise field for formulations of the noise equation, compared to NPN k' formulation (Equation (2)). Left to right: 0th, 1st and 2nd harmonic. Coordinates $x = 2$ and $x = 8$ denote the boundaries of the vibrating fuel pin. Peaks are due to denominator annulation or fortuitous numerator annulation.

computation and noise propagation [3]. The NS correction alone improves slightly the 1st harmonic, but has no impact on the 2nd harmonic. Specifically for the 2nd harmonic, we propose an intermediary *upward frequency* approximation ('Up'), similar to linear theory but including the noise source $-\delta\hat{\mathcal{B}}_1\hat{\phi}_1$ due to the 1st harmonic, itself computed by linear theory. This approximation recovers most of the NPN correction. Another intermediary *pseudo-NPN* formulation consists in computing the noise source from the critical flux and injecting it in a coupled fixed-source calculation of all non-null harmonics. This approach, explored in Ref. 2, improves the 1st harmonic inside the fuel, and more significantly the 2nd harmonic. However, it does not fare better than the 'Up' approximation for the 2nd harmonic, despite increased complexity; furthermore, we found it to be more sensitive to the value of h_{\max} . This altogether supports the finding that the NPN correction on the 2nd harmonic is essentially due to the coupling from the 1st to the 2nd harmonic. Finally, the results of the NPN k formulation (Equation (1)) are essentially equivalent to the k' formulation (Equation (2)), although the agreement worsens with increasing harmonic. This builds confidence in the new NPN formulation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The non-perturbative approach to the neutron noise equation offers the opportunity to accurately compute the neutron noise induced by fuel vibrations. It is suitable for Monte Carlo simulation, but can also be used with deterministic methods. In this work, the eigenvalue formulation proposed in Ref. 12 was rephrased in order to overcome some severe limitations. We successfully applied the novel formulation to a mechanical vibration model.

We also investigated the impact of the key parameters of the NPN algorithm. The required number of inactive generations, although larger than in standard eigenvalue calculations, is affordable. The frequency truncation may be kept relatively low, e.g. to the third harmonic if the calculation targets the first two harmonics. Besides, we showed that most of the non-perturbative correction is recovered with an *upward frequency* scheme that may easily implemented in existing noise solvers using linear theory.

Most importantly, the NPN noise computation enables a moderate performance gain, which was unexpected, the NPN formulation being less simplified than the linearized noise problem. This claim, if confirmed on different benchmarks and more realistic cases, would represent a significant improvement, paving the way towards more accurate and precise neutron noise simulations.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Pázsit and C. Demazière. “Noise Techniques in Nuclear Systems.” In D. G. Cacuci, editor, *Handbook of Nuclear Engineering*, pp. 1629–1737. Springer US, Boston, MA (2010).
- [2] A. Zoia, A. Rouchon, B. Gasse, C. Demazière, and P. Vinai. “Analysis of the Neutron Noise Induced by Fuel Assembly Vibrations.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 154**, p. 108061 (2021).
- [3] A. Rouchon, R. Sanchez, and I. Zmijarevic. “The New 3-D Multigroup Diffusion Neutron Noise Solver of APOLLO3 and a Theoretical Discussion of Fission-Modes Noise.” In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Mathematics and Computational Methods Applied to Nuclear Science and Engineering (M&C 2017)* (2017).
- [4] A. Rouchon, A. Zoia, and R. Sanchez. “A New Monte Carlo Method for Neutron Noise Calculations in the Frequency Domain.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 102**, pp. 465–475 (2017).
- [5] C. Demazière. “CORE SIM: A Multi-Purpose Neutronic Tool for Research and Education.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 38**(12), pp. 2698–2718 (2011).
- [6] P. Cosgrove, M. Kraus, and V. Raffuzzi. “A Memory-Efficient Neutron Noise Algorithm for Reactor Physics.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 201**, p. 110450 (2024).
- [7] T. Yamamoto. “Monte Carlo Method with Complex-Valued Weights for Frequency Domain Analyses of Neutron Noise.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 58**, pp. 72–79 (2013).
- [8] H. Belanger, D. Mancusi, A. Rouchon, and A. Zoia. “Variance Reduction and Noise Source Sampling Techniques for Monte Carlo Simulations of Neutron Noise Induced by Mechanical Vibrations.” *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 197**(4), pp. 534–557 (2023).
- [9] I. Pázsit. “The Linearization of Vibration-Induced Noise.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 11**(9), pp. 441–454 (1984).
- [10] R. Sanchez. “Some Comments in Neutron Noise Theory.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 86**, pp. 88–98 (2015).
- [11] A. Rouchon and R. Sanchez. “Analysis of Vibration-Induced Neutron Noise Using One-Dimension Noise Diffusion Theory.” In *Proceedings of the International Congress on Advances in Nuclear Power Plants 2025*, volume ICAPP 2015 proceedings (2015). URL <https://cea.hal.science/cea-02509066>.
- [12] A. Fauvel, A. Rouchon, D. Mancusi, and A. Zoia. “Monte Carlo Sampling Strategy for a Non-Perturbative Approach to the Neutron Noise Equation: A Proof of Concept.” In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Mathematics and Computational Methods Applied to Nuclear Science and Engineering (M&C 2025)*, pp. 996–1005 (2025).
- [13] H. Belanger. “HunterBelanger/Mgmc: MGMC v0.3.0.” Zenodo (2022).
- [14] A. Fauvel, A. Rouchon, D. Mancusi, and A. Zoia. “Convergence of Monte Carlo Methods for Neutron Noise.” *EPJ Web of Conferences*, **volume 302**, p. 08004 (2024).
- [15] H. Belanger, D. Mancusi, and A. Zoia. “Exact Weight Cancellation in Monte Carlo Eigenvalue Transport Problems.” *Physical Review E*, **volume 104**(1), p. 015306 (2021).
- [16] Y. Saad and M. H. Schultz. “GMRES: A Generalized Minimal Residual Algorithm for Solving Nonsymmetric Linear Systems.” *SIAM Journal on Scientific and Statistical Computing*, **volume 7**(3), pp. 856–869 (1986).
- [17] R. B. Lehoucq, D. C. Sorensen, and C. Yang. *ARPACK Users’ Guide*. Software, Environments, and Tools. Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics (1998).